

The Primordial Black Holes in the Preinflationary Era, Probabilities of Their Origination and Inflation Theories

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This work is a continuation of the study into the primordial black holes (**pbhs**) in the Schwarzschild-de Sitter Metric with small mass (ultralight) during the preinflationary era. Within the scope of natural assumptions, it has been shown that the quantum-gravitational corrections (**qgcs**) to the characteristics of such black holes can contribute to all the cosmological inflation parameters both in models with a single inflaton and multiple field inflation shifting them as compared to the semiclassical consideration. The probability for the formation of such **pbhs** has been studied in different patterns. It has been shown that, considering **qgcs**, this probability is growing practically always. Within the scope of a cosmological perturbation theory, it has been demonstrated that these **qgcs** for the preinflationary **qpbh** induce the metrics quantum deformation in General Relativity. It has been noted that, within the scope of this deformation, the energy-momentum tensor is retained.

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1. Introduction

The primordial black holes (**pbhs**) [1]–[3] in the Early Universe are due to gravitational collapse of the high-density matter [4]. In [5]–[7] a sufficiently accurate estimate of the mass **pbhs** $M(t_M)$ formed during the period of time t since the Big Bang has been obtained

$$M(t_M) \approx \frac{c^3 t_M}{G} \approx 10^{15} \left(\frac{t}{10^{-23} \text{ s}} \right) g. \quad (1)$$

As seen, for small times close to the Planckian time $t_M = t_p \approx 10^{-43} \text{ s}$, the mass of **pbhs** is close to the Planck mass $M(t_M) \approx 10^{-5} g$. The names of such black holes were varying with time: "mini-black holes", "micro-black holes", and, e.g. in [8], they were referred to as "ultralight primordial black holes". The author of this paper uses for such **pbhs** the name **quantum pbhs** (or **qpbhs**) introduced in [9],[10] and notes that quantum-gravitational effects for these objects could be significant. Of particular interest are

pbhs arising in the preinflationary era. In [11] a semiclassical approximation was used to study the problem of scalar perturbations due to such **pbhs**. But, considering that all the processes in this case proceed at very high energies E close to the Planckian $E \simeq E_p$, the inclusion of quantum-gravity corrections **qgcs** for these black holes in this pattern is necessary if quantum gravity exists [12]. Despite the fact that presently there is no self-consistent theory of quantum gravity, a consensus is reached on correctness of some approaches to the theory, specifically, replacement of the Heisenberg Uncertainty Principle (**HUP**) by the Generalized Uncertainty Principle (**GUP**) on going to high (Planck) energies, used in this paper.

Within the scope of a natural assumption based on the results from [11], in the present work the author studies the problem, how the above-mentioned **qgcs** for quantum **pbhs** can shift the inflationary parameters in the inflationary process. This paper continues a

study of primordial black holes in the preinflation period and of the inflationary models introduced for the first time in [13], [14]. As compared with the previously published results [13], in [14] consideration is given to the following:

a) shifts of the inflationary parameters for **multiple field inflation**;

b) dynamics of variations in the probability for the formation of the above-mentioned **pbhs** with regard to **qgcs** in different patterns;

c) the fact that, within the scope of a cosmological perturbation theory, **qgcs** for preinflationary **qpbh** induce the metric quantum deformation in General Relativity, the Energy - Momentum Tensor being retained within this deformation.

The paper is structured as follows.

Section 2 presents the preliminary results in the brief outline, showing how **qgcs** shift the inflationary parameters within a natural assumption from [11] in the inflationary model with a single inflation. In Section 3 the result is generalized to the case of **multiple-field inflation**. In Section 4 consideration is given to the dynamics of variations in the probability for the formation of **pbhs** with regard to **qgcs** in different patterns. Finally, Section 5 shows that, within the scope of a cosmological perturbation theory, **qgcs** for the preinflationary **qpbh** induce the metric quantum deformation in General Relativity with retention of the Energy - Momentum Tensor.

In what follows the normalization $c = \hbar = 1$ is used, for which we have $G = l_p^2$.

2. The preliminary results in the brief outline. PBHs in the preinflationary era and shifts of the inflation parameters

This section is a brief outline of the relevant results, previously obtained in [13], [14].

Let us consider the primordial black holes **pbhs** with small mass M (same radius r_M) in the Early

Universe during the preinflationary era with the Schwarzschild-de Sitter (SdS) metric [11]

$$ds^2 = -f(\tilde{r})dt^2 + \frac{d\tilde{r}^2}{f(\tilde{r})} + \tilde{r}^2 d\Omega^2 \quad (2)$$

where $f(\tilde{r}) = 1 - 2GM/\tilde{r} - \Lambda\tilde{r}^2/3 = 1 - 2GM/\tilde{r} - \tilde{r}^2/L^2$, $L = \sqrt{3/\Lambda} = H_0^{-1}$, M - black hole mass, Λ - cosmological constant, and $L = H_0^{-1}$ is the Hubble radius.

In general, such a black hole may have two different horizons corresponding to two different zeros $f(\tilde{r})$: event horizon of a black hole and cosmological horizon. This is just so in the case under study when a value of M is small [15],[16]. In the general case of $L \gg GM$, for the event horizon radius of a black hole having the metric (2), r_H takes the following form (formula (9) in [17]):

$$r_H \simeq 2GM \left[1 + \left(\frac{r_M}{L} \right)^2 \right], \quad (3)$$

where $r_M = 2MG$.

Then, due to the assumption concerning the initial smallness of Λ , we have $L \gg r_M$. In this case, to a high accuracy, the condition $r_H = r_M$ is fulfilled, i.e. for the considered (SdS) black holes **BH** we can use for this **BH** to a great accuracy the formulae for a Schwarzschild metric [19],[18]:

$$ds^2 = \left(1 - \frac{2MG}{r} \right) dt^2 - \left(1 - \frac{2MG}{r} \right)^{-1} dr^2 - r^2 d\Omega^2. \quad (4)$$

As **pbhs** under study are considered in the Early Universe during the preinflationary era, their radii (masses) are close to the Planckian values necessitating allowance for the quantum-gravitational corrections. In what follows we use the terminology from [9],[10], calling such **pbhs** *quantum* with the abbreviation **qpbhs**.

Specifically, for the energies on the order of Plank energies (quantum gravity scales) $E \simeq E_p$, the Heisenberg Uncertainty Principle (**HUP**) [20]

$$(\delta X)(\delta P) \geq \frac{\hbar}{2}, \quad (5)$$

may be replaced by the Generalized Uncertainty Principle (**GUP**) [21]

$$(\delta X)(\delta P) \geq \frac{\hbar}{2} \left\langle \exp \left(\frac{\alpha^2 l_p^2}{\hbar^2} P^2 \right) \right\rangle. \quad (6)$$

Then there is a possibility for existence of Planck Schwarzschild black hole, and accordingly of a Schwarzschild sphere (further referred to as "minimal") with the minimal mass M_0 and the minimal radius r_{min} (formula (20) in [21]) that is a theoretical minimal length r_{min} :

$$r_{min} = l_{min} = (\delta X)_0 = \sqrt{\frac{e}{2}} \alpha l_p, \quad M_0 = \frac{\alpha \sqrt{e}}{2\sqrt{2}} m_p, \quad (7)$$

where α - model-dependent parameters on the order of 1, e - base of natural logarithms, and $r_{min} \propto l_p, M_0 \propto m_p$.

In this case, due to GUP (6), the physics becomes nonlocal and the position of any point is determined accurate to l_{min} . It is impossible to ignore this nonlocality at the energies close to the Planck energy $E \approx E_p$, i.e. at the scales $l \propto l_p$ (equivalently we have $l \propto r_{min} = l_{min}$).

Then quantum-gravitational corrections **qgcs** generated by the GUP for **qpbh** with mass M and radius R has form [21],[13], [14]:

$$\begin{aligned} M_q &= M \exp \left(\frac{1}{2} W \left(-\frac{1}{e} \left(\frac{M_0}{M} \right)^2 \right) \right); \\ R_q &= 2M_q G = R \exp \left(\frac{1}{2} W \left(-\frac{1}{e} \left(\frac{M_0}{M} \right)^2 \right) \right) = R \exp \left(\frac{1}{2} W \left(-\frac{1}{e} \left(\frac{r_{min}}{r_M} \right)^2 \right) \right); \\ \exp \left(-\frac{1}{2} W \left(-\frac{1}{e} \left(\frac{M_0}{M} \right)^2 \right) \right) &= \left(1 + \frac{1}{2e} \left(\frac{M_0}{M} \right)^2 + \frac{5}{8e^2} \left(\frac{M_0}{M} \right)^4 + \frac{49}{48e^3} \left(\frac{M_0}{M} \right)^6 + \dots \right), \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where $W \left(-\frac{1}{e} \left(\frac{M_0}{M} \right)^2 \right) = W \left(-\frac{1}{e} \left(\frac{r_{min}}{r_M} \right)^2 \right) = W \left(-\frac{1}{e} \left(\frac{A_0}{A} \right) \right)$ - value at the corresponding point of the Lambert W-function $W(u)$ satisfying the equation (formulae (1.5) in [22] and (9) in [21])

$$W(u) e^{W(u)} = u. \quad (9)$$

$W(u)$ is the multifunction for complex variable $u = x + yi$. However, for real $u = x, -1/e \leq u < 0, W(u)$ is the single-valued continuous function having two branches denoted by $W_0(u)$ and $W_{-1}(u)$, and for real $u = x, u \geq 0$ there is only one branch $W_0(u)$ [22]. (Here A_0, A - event horizon area for a minimal black hole and the present **qpbh**, respectively.)

As shown in [21], the quantities $\exp \left(\pm \frac{1}{2} W \left(-\frac{1}{e} \left(\frac{M_0}{M} \right)^2 \right) \right)$ are expanded into

a series in terms of the small parameter $(M_0/M)^2$. It be showed in [14] that the quantum-gravitational correction (**qgcs**) (8) presents a *deformation* (or more exactly, the *quantum deformation* of a classical black-holes theory from the viewpoint of the paper [23] with the deformation parameter A_0/A):

$$\frac{A_0}{A} = \frac{4\pi r_{min}^2}{4\pi r_M^2} = \frac{l_{min}^2}{r_M^2}, \quad (10)$$

where $r_{min} = l_{min}$ is the horizon radius of minimal **qpbh** from formula (7). It should be noted that this deformation parameter

$$l_{min}^2/r_M^2 \doteq \alpha_{r_M} \quad (11)$$

has been introduced by the author in his earlier works [24]-[29], where he studied deformation of

quantum mechanics at Planck scales in terms of the deformed quantum mechanical density matrix. In the Schwarzschild black hole case $\alpha_{r_M} = l_{min}^2 \mathcal{K}$ is the Gaussian curvature $\mathcal{K} =$

$1/\alpha_{r_M}$ of the black-hole event horizon surface [30].

The metric (2) is described in terms of the conformal time η [11]:

$$ds^2 = a^2(\eta) \left\{ -d\eta^2 + \left(1 + \frac{\mu^3 \eta^3}{r^3}\right)^{4/3} \left[\left(\frac{1 - \mu^3 \eta^3 / r^3}{1 + \mu^3 \eta^3 / r^3}\right)^2 dr^2 + r^2 d\Omega^2 \right] \right\}, \quad (12)$$

where $\mu = (GMH_0/2)^{1/3}$, H_0 – de Sitter-Hubble parameter and scale factor, a – conformal time function η :

$$a(\eta) = -1/(H_0\eta), \eta < 0. \quad (13)$$

Here r satisfies the condition $r_0 < r < \infty$ and a value of $r_0 = -\mu\eta$ in the reference frame of (12) conforms to singularity of the back hole.

From formula (3) we have

$$\mu = (r_M H_0 / 4)^{1/3}, \quad (14)$$

where r_M is the radius of a black hole with the SdS Schwarzschild-de Sitter metric (2). Also, in [13],[14] consideration has been given to the case $\mu = const$ for different processes (steady state, absorption, and emission) with due regard for **qgcs** and disregarding them.

It is assumed that after termination of these processes μ is unaltered with regard to **qgcs**, i.e. in formula (14) we have $\mu = (r_M H_0 / 4)^{1/3} = (r_{M_q} H_{0,q} / 4)^{1/3}$, where $r_{M_q}, H_{0,q}$ – values of r_M, H_0 , respectively, with due regard for **qgcs**.

The Stationary picture.

From the start of creation, the primordial black hole, with the mass M and the event horizon area A , is considered in the absence of absorption

and radiation processes. It may be assumed that such **qpbh** was generated immediately before the onset of inflation, when there were no absorption and radiation processes. On the other hand, this picture is completely consistent with the paradigm in [9], [10] presuming the absence of Hawking radiation for **qpbh**, with the mass and the event horizon radius close to the Planckian values $M \approx m_p, r_M \approx l_p$.

As $\mu = const$ and **pbh** we consider in the stationary state, then, with regard for **qgcs**, replacement $r_M \mapsto r_{M_q}$ in this formula leads to replacement of $H_0 \rightarrow H_{0,q}$, and meeting the condition

$$\mu = (r_M H_0 / 4)^{1/3} = (r_{M_q} H_{0,q} / 4)^{1/3}. \quad (15)$$

Here $r_{M_q} = R_q$ from the general formula (8).

Based on the last formula and formulae (11),(8) it directly follows that

$$\begin{aligned} H_{0,q} &= H_0 \exp \left(-\frac{1}{2} W \left(-\frac{1}{e} \left(\frac{M_0}{M} \right)^2 \right) \right) = \\ &= H_0 \exp \left(-\frac{1}{2} W \left(-\frac{1}{e} \alpha_{r_M} \right) \right). \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

Then **qgc** for the scale factor $a(\eta)$ (13)

$$\begin{aligned}
 a(\eta) &\rightarrow a(\eta)_q \doteq -1/(H_{0,q}\eta) = -1/(H_0 \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\left(\frac{M_0}{M}\right)^2\right)\right)\eta) = \\
 &= -1/(H_0 \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_M}\right)\right)\eta) = a(\eta) \exp\left(\frac{1}{2}W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_M}\right)\right), \eta < 0,
 \end{aligned} \tag{17}$$

and for the Hubble parameter in general case $H(\eta) \doteq H$

$$H = a'(\eta)/a^2(\eta) \mapsto H_q(\eta) = a'(\eta)_q/a^2(\eta)_q \tag{18}$$

As directly follows from the last formula, in this pattern H_0 and H are identically transformed, i.e. we have

$$H \mapsto H_q = H \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_M}\right)\right) \tag{19}$$

Because the potential energy of inflation V is related to the Hubble parameter H by the Friedmann equation (formula (12.12) in [31]) $H^2 = 8\pi V/(3M_p^2)$, from (16) we can derive a "shift" for V that is due to quantum-gravitational corrections for the primordial Schwarzschild black hole with the mass M as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 [V = 3M_p^2 H^2/(8\pi)] &\mapsto V_q = 3M_p^2 H_q^2/(8\pi) = 3 \exp\left(-W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_M}\right)\right) M_p^2 H^2/(8\pi) \\
 &= \exp\left(-W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_M}\right)\right) V,
 \end{aligned} \tag{20}$$

In a similar way, taking account of **qgcs** for quantum **pbhs** (formulae ((8),(16)–(19)), we can

find these "shifts" for all inflationary parameters, in particular

$$\begin{aligned}
 (a \sim H^{-1}) &\mapsto a_q \sim H_q^{-1}; & (V \sim H^2) &\mapsto V_q \sim H_q^2; & (\dot{\phi} = -\frac{V'(\phi)}{3H} \sim H) &\mapsto \dot{\phi}_q = (-\frac{V'(\phi)}{3H})_q \sim H_q; \\
 (\dot{H} = \frac{1}{2m_p}(\frac{8\pi}{3V})^{1/2}V'(\phi)\dot{\phi} \sim H^2) &\mapsto \dot{H}_q = \frac{1}{2m_p}[(\frac{8\pi}{3V})^{1/2}V'(\phi)\dot{\phi}]_q \sim H_q^2; \\
 (\ddot{\phi} = -\frac{m_p^2}{8\pi}(\frac{V''}{V} - \frac{1}{2}(\frac{V'}{V})^2)H\dot{\phi} \sim H^2) &\mapsto \ddot{\phi}_q \sim H_q^2, \dots
 \end{aligned} \tag{21}$$

with retention of some part of them on the transformation $H \mapsto H_q$, for example it is easy to check retention of the deceleration parameters

$\epsilon, \tilde{\eta}$ [31]:

$$\begin{aligned}\epsilon &= -\frac{\dot{H}}{H^2} = m_p \frac{V'^2}{V^2} = \epsilon_q = -\frac{\dot{H}_q}{H_q^2} = m_p \frac{V_q'^2}{V_q^2}, \\ \tilde{\eta} &= \frac{m_p^2 V''}{8\pi V} = \tilde{\eta}_q.\end{aligned}\quad (22)$$

Here in the last two formulae (21),(22) a point means differentiation with respect to t , but a prime means differentiation with respect to the field ϕ . Let us denote the second deceleration parameter $\tilde{\eta}$ instead of η [31], to avoid confusion with the conformal time.

As we have $\epsilon = \epsilon_q, \tilde{\eta} = \tilde{\eta}_q$, the slow-roll conditions (formula (22) in [31]) in the inflationary scenario with regard to **qgcs** for **qpbhs** remains unaltered.

Due to formulae (8) and (11), all the above-mentioned shifts of the inflationary parameters generated by **qgcs** for **qpbhs** in the preinflationary period may be series expanded in terms of the small parameter $(M_0/M)^2$ (same α_{rM}).

Similarly, in [14] the above-mentioned shifts of the inflationary parameters due to **qgcs** for **qpbhs** have been considered in the preinflationary period for the BH evaporation and BH particle-absorption processes.

3. Multiple-field inflation

The foregoing results may be generalized to the case of multiple scalar fields. Such models are presently widely used in inflationary cosmology (for example, see [32]). In this pattern for a single, spatially homogeneous scalar field with the Klein-Gordon equation we have

$$\ddot{\phi} + 3H\dot{\phi} = -\frac{dV}{d\phi}, \quad (23)$$

and the Friedmann constraint

$$3H^2 = 8\pi G \left[\frac{1}{2}\dot{\phi}^2 + V(\phi) \right]. \quad (24)$$

is replaced by multiple scalar fields with the Klein-Gordon equation [32]

$$\ddot{\phi}_I + 3H\dot{\phi}_I = -\frac{\partial}{\partial\phi_I} \left(\sum_J U_J \right), \quad (25)$$

where the potential energy is given by the following sum

$$V = \sum_J U_J. \quad (26)$$

and the Friedmann constraint:

$$3H^2 = 8\pi G \left(V + \sum_I \frac{1}{2}\dot{\phi}_I^2 \right). \quad (27)$$

We can verify that if, provided the formula (21) is valid, we demand that the effect of **qgcs** for **qpbhs** in the preinflationary era on the inflation parameters $\dot{\phi}_I, \ddot{\phi}_I, U_J$ be analogous to the formula (21), i.e. as

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{\phi}_I &\mapsto \dot{\phi}_{I,q} = \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{rM}\right)\right)\dot{\phi}_I; \\ \ddot{\phi}_I &\mapsto \ddot{\phi}_{I,q} = \exp\left(-W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{rM}\right)\right)\ddot{\phi}_I; \\ U_J &\mapsto U_{J,q} = \exp\left(-W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{rM}\right)\right)U_J,\end{aligned}\quad (28)$$

in this case in a model of the *multiple-field inflation* we have a self-consistent shift of the inflation parameters with regard to **qgcs** for **qpbhs** in the preinflationary era.

4. Quantum-gravity corrections for the probabilities of pbhs formation in the preinflationary era

The results for the case [32] presented in this section have been derived in [14] and are extended now due to consideration of $\mu \neq const$. First, recall the correction of the probability for the formation of PBHs in the pattern $\mu = const$.

4.1. Case of $\mu = const.$

There is the problem of estimating the probability of occurrence for **pbhs** with Schwarzschild-de Sitter **SdS** metric (2) in the pre-inflation epoch. This problem has been studied in [11] without due regard for **qgcs**. Let us demonstrate that consideration of **qgcs** in this case makes the probability of arising such **qpbhs** higher. Similar to [11], it is assumed that in pre-inflation period non-relativistic particles with the mass $m < M_p$ are dominant (Section 3 in [11]). For convenience, let us denote the Schwarzschild radius r_M by R_S . When denoting, in analogy with [11], by $N(R, t)$ the number of particles in a *comoving* ball with the physical radius $R = R(t)$ and the volume V_R at time t , in the case under study this number (formula (3.9) in [11]) will have by **qgc**:

$$N(R, t) \mapsto N(R, t)_q; \quad \left(\langle N(R, t) \rangle = \frac{m_p^2 H^2 R^3}{2m} \right) \\ \mapsto \left(\langle N(R, t)_q \rangle = \frac{m_p^2 H_q^2 R^3}{2m} \right). \quad (29)$$

Here the first part of the last formula agrees with formula (3.9) in [11], whereas H, H_q in this case are in agreement with formulae (18),(19). And from (19) it follows that

$$\langle N(R, t)_q \rangle = \langle N(R, t) \rangle \exp \left(-W \left(-\frac{1}{e} \left(\frac{M_0}{M} \right)^2 \right) \right). \quad (30)$$

According to (8), it is necessary to replace the Schwarzschild radius R_S by

$$R_{S,q} = R_S \exp \left(\frac{1}{2} W \left(-\frac{1}{e} \left(\frac{M_0}{M} \right)^2 \right) \right).$$

Then from the general formula $N(R_S, t) = \langle N(R_S, t) \rangle + \delta N(R_S, t)$, used because of the replacement of $R_S \mapsto R_{S,q}$, we obtain an analog of (3.12) from [11]

$$\delta N > \delta N_{cr,q} \doteq \frac{m_p^2 R_{S,q}}{2m} - \langle N(R_S, t)_q \rangle = \frac{m_p^2 R_{S,q}}{2m} [1 - (HR_S)^2] \\ = \frac{m_p^2 R_S}{2m} [1 - (HR_S)^2] \exp \left(\frac{1}{2} W \left(-\frac{1}{e} \left(\frac{M_0}{M} \right)^2 \right) \right) = \delta N_{cr} \exp \left(\frac{1}{2} W \left(-\frac{1}{e} \left(\frac{M_0}{M} \right)^2 \right) \right). \quad (31)$$

In the last formula in square brackets we should have $(H_q R_{S,q})^2$ instead of $(HR_S)^2$ but, as we consider the case $\mu = const$, these quantities are coincident.

It should be noted that here the following condition is used:

$$HR_S < 1, \quad (32)$$

i.e. Schwarzschild radius R_S less than Hubble radius, $R_S < R_H = 1/H$. As we have

$$\exp \left(\frac{1}{2} W \left(-\frac{1}{e} \left(\frac{M_0}{M} \right)^2 \right) \right) < 1, \text{ then}$$

$$\delta N_{cr,q} < \delta N_{cr}. \quad (33)$$

Considering that for the formation of a Schwarzschild black hole with the radius R_S it is required that, due to statistical fluctuations, the number of particles $N(R_S, t)$ with the mass m within the black hole volume $V_{R_S} = 4/3\pi R_S^3$ be in agreement with the condition [11]

$$N(R_S, t) > R_S M_p^2 / (2m), \quad (34)$$

which, according to **qgc** in the formula of (8), may be replaced by

$$N(R_{S,q}, t) > R_{S,q}M_p^2/(2m) \\ = \exp\left(\frac{1}{2}W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\left(\frac{M_0}{M}\right)^2\right)\right)R_{S,q}M_p^2/(2m). \quad (35)$$

As follows from these expressions, with regard to **qgc** for the formation of **pbh** in the pre-inflation period, the number of the corresponding particles may be lower than for a black hole without such regard, leading to a higher probability of the formation.

Such a conclusion may be made by comparison of this probability in a semi-classical consideration (formula (3.13) in [11])

$$P(\delta N(R_S, t) > \delta N_{\text{cr}}(R_S, t)) = \int_{\delta N_{\text{cr}}}^{\infty} d(\delta N)P(\delta N) \quad (36)$$

and with due regard for **qgc**

$$P(\delta N(R_{S,q}, t) > \delta N_{\text{cr}}(R_{S,q}, t)) = \int_{\delta N_{\text{cr},q}}^{\infty} d(\delta N)P(\delta N). \quad (37)$$

Considering that in the last two integrals the integrands take positive values and are the same, whereas the integration domain in the second integral is wider due to (33), we have

$$\int_{\delta N_{\text{cr},q}}^{\infty} d(\delta N)P(\delta N) = \int_{\delta N_{\text{cr}}}^{\delta N_{\text{cr}}} d(\delta N)P(\delta N) + \int_{\delta N_{\text{cr}}}^{\infty} d(\delta N)P(\delta N) > \int_{\delta N_{\text{cr}}}^{\infty} d(\delta N)P(\delta N). \quad (38)$$

As follows from the last three formulae, in the case under study the probability that the above-mentioned **pbhs** will be formed is higher with due regard for **qgcs**. The above calculations are supported by the general formula for the **pbhs** formation probability in this case [11]:

$$P(\mu, m, H) = \frac{\mu^{3/2}}{1 - 16\mu^6} \sqrt{\frac{4mH}{\pi m_p^2}} \left(\frac{H_*}{H}\right)^{\frac{2+3w}{3(1+w)}} \\ \times \exp\left(-\frac{m_p^2(1 - 16\mu^6)^2}{16mH\mu^3} \left(\frac{H}{H_*}\right)^{\frac{2(2+3w)}{3(1+w)}}\right) \quad (39)$$

Here H_* is the Hubble rate at the initial time t_* , $w = p_0/\rho_0$, p_0 , ρ_0 is the background fluid pressure and density respectively. With regard to **qgcs**, the quantity $P(\mu, m, H)$ is replaced by $P(\mu, m, H)_q$:

$$P(\mu, m, H) \mapsto P(\mu, m, H)_q = \frac{\mu^{3/2}}{1 - 16\mu^6} \sqrt{\frac{4mH_q}{\pi m_p^2}} \left(\frac{H_{*,q}}{H_q}\right)^{\frac{2+3w}{3(1+w)}} \exp\left(-\frac{m_p^2(1 - 16\mu^6)^2}{16mH_q\mu^3} \left(\frac{H_q}{H_{*,q}}\right)^{\frac{2(2+3w)}{3(1+w)}}\right), \quad (40)$$

where, due to (19), we have $H_q = H \exp(-\frac{1}{2}W(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{R(A)}))$, $H_{*,q} = H_* \exp(-\frac{1}{2}W(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{R(A)}))$. Then it is clear that $P(\mu, m, H)_q > P(\mu, m, H)$, as these two expressions differ in the second and the first factors of the exponent, which are knowingly greater in $P(\mu, m, H)_q > P(\mu, m, H)$ because $H_q > H$.

4.2. Case of $\mu \neq const.$

We can analyze a change in estimation of the probability for the formation of **qpbh** when $\mu \neq$

const. In calculations of **qgcs** for **pbh** according to formulae from Section 2 only $\mu \neq const$ is changing, whereas the cosmological parameters remain unaltered. Then in formula (12) we have the substitution:

$$(\mu = (GMH_0/2)^{1/3}) \mapsto (\mu_q = (GM_qH_0/2)^{1/3}), \quad (41)$$

and M_q is the mass of **pbh** with regard to **qgc** from formula (8). In the formula (31) we have the substitution

$$\begin{aligned} \delta N > \delta N_{cr,q} &\doteq \frac{m_p^2 R_{S,q}}{2m} - \langle N(R_S, t)_q \rangle = \frac{m_p^2 R_{S,q}}{2m} [1 - (HR_{S,q})^2] \\ &= \frac{m_p^2 R_S \exp(\frac{1}{2}W(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{R_S}))}{2m} [1 - H^2 R_S^2 \exp(W(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{R_S}))]. \end{aligned} \quad (42)$$

To understand variations in the probability for the formation of **qpbh** as compared with the case when **qgcs** are disregarded, in our consideration we compare the last expression with the corresponding quantity $\delta N_{cr} = \frac{m_p^2 R_S}{2m} [1 -$

$(HR_S)^2]$. Dividing the last expression and the right-hand side of (42) by the same positive number $\frac{m_p^2 R_S}{2m}$ and subtracting the second from the first one, we obtain the following:

$$\begin{aligned} &\frac{m_p^2 R_S}{2m} [1 - H^2 R_S^2] - \frac{m_p^2 R_S}{2m} \exp\left(\frac{1}{2}W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{R_S}\right)\right) [1 - H^2 R_S^2 \exp\left(W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{R_S}\right)\right)] \\ &\sim [1 - H^2 R_S^2 + H^2 R_S^2 \exp\left(\frac{3}{2}W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{R_S}\right)\right) - \exp\left(\frac{1}{2}W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{R_S}\right)\right)] \\ &= 1 - \exp\left(\frac{1}{2}W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{R_S}\right)\right) + H^2 R_S^2 (\exp\left(\frac{3}{2}W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{R_S}\right)\right) - 1). \end{aligned} \quad (43)$$

As a result, in accordance with the formula (38), in this scenario a probability for the formation of **qpbh** with regard to **qgcs** is higher if the following condition is fulfilled: (33) $\delta N_{cr,q} < N_{cr}$, i.e. if $1 - \exp\left(\frac{1}{2}W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{R_S}\right)\right)$

$+H^2 R_S^2 (\exp\left(\frac{3}{2}W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{R_S}\right)\right) - 1) > 0$. Using the obvious inequality $1 - \exp\left(\frac{3}{2}W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{R_S}\right)\right) > 0$ and the formula for a difference in the cubed numbers 1 and $\exp\left(\frac{1}{2}W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{R_S}\right)\right)$, we have the inequality

$$H^2 R_S^2 < \frac{1 - \exp\left(\frac{1}{2}W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{R_S}\right)\right)}{1 - \exp\left(\frac{3}{2}W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{R_S}\right)\right)} = \frac{1}{1 + \exp\left(\frac{1}{2}W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{R_S}\right)\right) + \exp\left(W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{R_S}\right)\right)}. \quad (44)$$

In the case under consideration, to make the probability for the formation of **qpbh** with regard to **qgcs** higher than a similar probability but

without regard to **qgcs**, it is sufficient to replace the condition $HR_S < 1$ in the formula (32) by the following condition:

$$HR_S < \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + \exp\left(\frac{1}{2}W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{R_S}\right)\right) + \exp\left(W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{R_S}\right)\right)}}. \quad (45)$$

Note that R_S is small and close to $r_{min} = l_{min}$ from the formulae (7),(10),(11). Then for α_{R_S} from (11) it is correct that $\alpha_{R_S} \approx 1$ and hence, in line with [22] $W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\right) = -1$ and $\exp\left(\frac{1}{2}W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{R_S}\right)\right)$, $\exp\left(W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{R_S}\right)\right)$ is also small. Because of this, a value of the right side in (45) is close to 1, from where it follows that the condition (45) is only slightly different from the initial condition $HR_S < 1$.

5. Some commentaries on quantum deformation of metrics, energy–momentum tensor in frame of cosmological perturbations theory

5.1. Quantum deformation of metrics

Based on the formula (17), within the scope of a cosmological perturbation theory we can derive the quantum deformation of the fundamental quantities in General Relativity due to **qgcs** for the preinflationary **qpbh**.

In particular for the components of a spatially flat FRW metric perturbed up to second order in general case we have [33], [34]

$$g_{00} = -a^2(\tau) \left(1 + 2\phi^{(1)} + \phi^{(2)}\right), \quad g_{0i} = a^2(\tau) \left(\partial_i \omega^{(1)} + \frac{1}{2} \partial_i \omega^{(2)} + \frac{1}{2} \omega_i^{(2)}\right)$$

$$g_{ij} = a^2(\tau) \left[\left(1 - 2\psi^{(1)} - \psi^{(2)}\right) \delta_{ij} + D_{ij} \left(\chi^{(1)} + \frac{1}{2} \chi^{(2)}\right) + \frac{1}{2} \left(\partial_i \chi_j^{(2)} + \partial_j \chi_i^{(2)} + \chi_{ij}^{(2)}\right) \right] \quad (46)$$

where indexes (1), (2) are the perturbations orders of the metric for the arbitrary function $\vartheta \doteq$

$\phi, \hat{\omega}_i, \dots$ in the right side of the last equation

within the scope of a cosmological perturbation theory [33],[34]. For corresponding **QD** induced by **qpbh**, due to the formulae (17), we have the substitution:

$$\begin{aligned} g_{00} &\mapsto g_{00,q} = \exp\left(W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_M}\right)\right) g_{00}, \\ g_{0i} &\mapsto g_{0i,q} = \exp\left(W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_M}\right)\right) g_{0i}, \\ g_{ij} &\mapsto g_{ij,q} = \exp\left(W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_M}\right)\right) g_{ij}. \end{aligned} \quad (47)$$

Consequently, for the contravariant metric tensor we have

$$\begin{aligned} g^{00} &= -a^{-2}(\tau) \left(1 - 2\phi^{(1)} - \phi^{(2)} + 4\left(\phi^{(1)}\right)^2 - \partial^i\omega^{(1)}\partial_i\omega^{(1)}\right), \\ g^{0i} &= a^{-2}(\tau) \left[\partial^i\omega^{(1)} + \frac{1}{2}\left(\partial^i\omega^{(2)} + \omega^{i(2)}\right) + 2\left(\psi^{(1)} - \phi^{(1)}\right)\partial^i\omega^{(1)} - \partial^i\omega^{(1)}D^i{}_k\chi^{(1)}\right], \\ g^{ij} &= a^{-2}(\tau) \left[\left(1 + 2\psi^{(1)} + \psi^{(2)} + 4\left(\psi^{(1)}\right)^2\right)\delta^{ij} - D^{ij}\left(\chi^{(1)} + \frac{1}{2}\chi^{(2)}\right) - \frac{1}{2}\left(\partial^i\chi^{j(2)} + \partial^j\chi^{i(2)} + \chi^{ij(2)}\right) - \partial^i\omega^{(1)}\partial^j\omega^{(1)} - 4\psi^{(1)}D^{ij}\chi^{(1)} + D^{ik}\chi^{(1)}D^j{}_k\chi^{(1)}\right]. \end{aligned} \quad (48)$$

and from the same formula (17) be valid

$$\begin{aligned} g^{00} &\mapsto g^{00,q} = \exp\left(-W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_M}\right)\right) g^{00}, \\ g^{0i} &\mapsto g^{0i,q} = \exp\left(-W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_M}\right)\right) g^{0i}, \\ g^{ij} &\mapsto g^{ij,q} = \exp\left(-W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_M}\right)\right) g^{ij}. \end{aligned} \quad (49)$$

As follows from the foregoing formulae, we have

$$g_{\mu\nu}g^{\nu\lambda} = g_{\mu\nu,q}g^{\nu\lambda,q} = \delta_\mu^\lambda. \quad (50)$$

5.2. Invariance of the energy-momentum tensor

We can demonstrate that **QD** retains the energy-momentum tensor **EMT** when this **EMT** of perfect fluid is given by

$$T^\mu{}_\nu = (\rho + P)u^\mu u_\nu + P\delta^\mu{}_\nu \quad (51)$$

with the corresponding energy and pressure ρ, P and the fluid four-velocity u^μ meeting the constraint [34]

$$g^{\mu\nu}u_\mu u_\nu = -1 \quad (52)$$

Then four-velocity u^μ has the form

$$u^\mu = \frac{1}{a} \left(\delta_0^\mu + v_{(1)}^\mu + \frac{1}{2}v_{(2)}^\mu\right) \quad (53)$$

and $v_{(i)}^\mu, i = 1, 2$ is expressed in terms of $\phi^{(i)}, \omega^{(i)}$. Evidently, in virtue **QD**

$$u^\mu \mapsto u_q^\mu = \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}W\left(-\frac{1}{e}\alpha_{r_M}\right)\right) u^\mu \quad (54)$$

Similarly for u_ν we have

$$\begin{aligned}
u_0 &= a \left(-1 - \phi^{(1)} - \frac{1}{2}\phi^{(2)} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\phi^{(1)} \right)^2 - \frac{1}{2} v_i^{(1)} v_{(1)}^i \right), \\
u_i &= a \left(v_i^{(1)} + \partial_i \omega^{(1)} + \frac{1}{2} v_i^{(2)} + \frac{1}{2} \omega_i^{(2)} - \phi^{(1)} \partial_i \omega^{(1)} - 2\psi^{(1)} v_i^{(1)} + D_{ij} \chi^{(1)} v_{(1)}^j \right). \quad (55)
\end{aligned}$$

and in this case **QD** acts as

$$u_\nu \mapsto u_{\nu,q} = \exp \left(\frac{1}{2} W \left(-\frac{1}{e} \alpha_{r_M} \right) \right) u_\nu \quad (56)$$

From the foregoing calculations and from formula (49) it follows that

$$T^\mu{}_\nu = (\rho + P) u^\mu u_\nu + P \delta^\mu{}_\nu = (\rho + P) u_q^\mu u_{\nu,q} + P \delta^\mu{}_\nu \doteq [T^\mu{}_\nu]_q, \quad g^{\mu\nu} u_\mu u_\nu = g^{\mu\nu,q} u_{\mu,q} u_{\nu,q} = -1. \quad (57)$$

6. Conclusion and further steps

This paper demonstrates the way to calculate in the explicit form the quantum-gravitational corrections for the basic cosmological parameters in the inflationary scenario which are due to **pbhs** originating during the pre-inflationary period of time. As follows from the above-mentioned formulae, for such black holes these corrections are especially great and may be significant for the basic parameters of inflation. Because of this, they are important for studies of the processes in the very early Universe. According to the results in [35], a local quantum field theory [36] has the upper applicability boundary \tilde{E} that is considerably lower than the Planck energy $\tilde{E} \ll E_p$. It is clear that the quantum-gravitational corrections are most significant within the energy range $E, \tilde{E} < E \leq E_p$.

It is known that inflationary cosmology is characterized by *cosmological perturbations* of different nature (scalar, vector, tensor) [31],[37],[33], though vector perturbations are

usually ignored as they die out fast. Proceeding from the results of this paper, the following problems may be formulated for further studies:

6.1 Investigation of the "shifts" (changes) for the parameters of cosmological perturbations on inflation which are generated by **qgcs** for **pbhs** in the preinflationary period;

6.2 Elucidation, how close is the connection of these "shifts" with the general approaches to **qgcs** for cosmological perturbations on inflation (for example, see [38]);

6.3 What is the applicability of the obtained results to other (noninflationary) cosmological models (for example, cyclic cosmology models [39]).

Conflict of interests

The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this work.

References

- [1] Y. B. Zeldovich and I. D. Novikov. The Hypothesis of Cores Retarded during Expansion and the Hot Cosmological Model, *Soviet Astron.J.* **10**, 602 (1967). (Engl. Transl.)
- [2] Stephen Hawking. Gravitationally Collapsed Objects of Very Low Mass. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society* **152**, 75 (1971).
- [3] B. J. Carr, S. W. Hawking. Black Holes in the Early Universe. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society* **168**, 399 (1974).
- [4] Anne M. Green and Bradley J. Kavanagh. Primordial Black Holes as a dark matter candidate. *Phys. G: Nucl. Part. Phys.* **48**, 043001 (2021).
- [5] B. J. Carr. The Primordial black hole mass spectrum. *Astrophys. J.* **168**, 201 (1975).
- [6] B. J. Carr. Primordial black holes as a probe of cosmology and high energy physics. *Lect. Notes in Phys.*, **631**, 301 (2003).
- [7] B. J. Carr. *Primordial black holes - recent developments*. [arXiv:astro-ph/0504034], 22nd Texas Symposium at Stanford 12-17 December 2004
- [8] S.Profumo. *Ultralight Primordial Black Holes*. arXiv:2405.00546 [astro-ph.HE]
- [9] Xavier Calmet, Wei Gong, Stephen D.H. Hsu. Colorful quantum black holes at the LHC. *Phys.Lett.B.* **668**, 20 (2008).
- [10] Xavier Calmet. Fundamental Physics with Black Holes. Chapter 1 in "Quantum aspects of black holes Ed.Xavier Calmet Fundamental Theories of Physics, vol.178, pp.1-26, Springer International Publishing Switzerland 2015
- [11] Tomislav Prokopec and Paul Reska. Scalar cosmological perturbations from inflationary black holes. *Journal of Cosmology and Astroparticle Physics*, **03**, 050 (2011).
- [12] Claus Kiefer. *Quantum Gravity.Third Edition* (Oxford University Press,United Kingdom 2012).
- [13] A. E. Shalyt-Margolin. Primordial black holes in the early Universe, quantum-gravitational corrections and inflationary cosmology. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of Belarus. Physics and Mathematics series*, **60**, 225 (2024).
- [14] Alexander Shalyt-Margolin. The Quantum Primordial Black Holes, Dimensionless Small Parameter. *Inflationary Cosmology and Non-Gaussianity, Annals of Physics*, **474**, 169930 (2025).
- [15] H. Nariai. On some static solutions of Einstein's gravitational field equations in a spherically symmetric case. *Sci. Rep. Tohoku Univ.*, **34**, 160 (1950).
- [16] H. Nariai. On a new cosmological solution of Einstein's field equations of gravitation. *Sci. Rep. Tohoku Univ.*, **35**, 62 (1951).
- [17] Roberto Casadio, Andrea Giugno, Andrea Giusti, Michele Lenzi. Quantum formation of primordial black holes, *General Relativity and Gravitation*, **51**, 103 (2019).
- [18] Valeri P. Frolov, Igor D. Novikov. *Black Hole Physics: Basic Concepts and New Developments* (Kluwer Academic Publishers, 1997).
- [19] R.M.Wald. *General Relativity* (University of Chicago Press, Chicago, Ill,USA 1984).
- [20] W.Heisenberg. Uber den anschaulichen Inhalt der quantentheoretischen Kinematik und Mechanik. *Z. Phys.*,**43**, 172 (1927).
- [21] K. Nouicer. Quantum-corrected black hole thermodynamics to all orders in the Planck length. *Phys.Lett B.*,**646**, 63 (2007).
- [22] R.M. Corless, G.H. Gonnet, D.E. Hare, D.J. Jerrey and D.E. Knuth. On the Lambert W function. *Adv. Comput. Math.*, **5**, 329 (1996).
- [23] L.Faddeev. Mathematical View on Evolution of Physics. *Priroda*, **5**, 11 (1989).
- [24] A.E. Shalyt-Margolin. Quantum mechanics at Planck scale and density matrix. *Intern. J. Mod. Phys. D* **12**, 1265 (2003).
- [25] A.E.Shalyt-Margolin. Unitarity in Generalized Quantum Mechanics and Hawking's Information Problem for Black Holes. *Int. J.Nonlinear Phenomena in Complex Systems*, **7(3)**, 283 (2004).
- [26] A.E. Shalyt-Margolin, V.I. Strazhev, and A.Ya. Tregubovich. The Density Matrix Deformation and Symmetry Breakdown in the Early Universe. *Int. J. Nonlinear Phenomena in Complex Systems*, **8(3)**, 240 (2005).
- [27] A.E.Shalyt-Margolin and J.G. Suarez. Deformation of Density Matrix at The Early Universe and Bekenstein-Hawking Formula. *Int. J.Nonlinear Phenomena in Complex Systems*, **7(2)**, 129 (2005).
- [28] A.E.Shalyt-Margolin and V.I.Strazhev. Vacuum Energy and Small Parameter at Planck Scale. *Int. J. Nonlinear Phenomena in Complex Systems*, **12(1)**, 102 (2009).
- [29] A.E. Shalyt-Margolin and A.Ya. Tregubovich. Deformed density matrix and generalized uncertainty relation in thermodynamics. *Mod. Phys. Lett. A*, **19**, 71 (2004).
- [30] Wolfgang Kuhnel. *Differential Geometry:*

- Curves, Surfaces, Manifolds.* (American Mathematical Society, United Kingdom 2006).
- [31] Dmitri S.Gorbunov and Valery A.Rubakov. *Introduction to the Theory of the Early Universe. Cosmological Perturbation and Inflation Theory* (World Scientific, Singapore 2011).
- [32] David Wands. Multiple field inflation. Lect. Notes in Phys., **738**, 275 (2008).
- [33] V.Mukhanov. *Physical Foundation of Cosmology* (Cambridge University Press, 2005).
- [34] N. Bartolo, E. Komatsu, S. Matarrese and A. Riotto. Non-Gaussianity from inflation: Theory and observations. Phys. Rept. **402**, 103 (2004).
- [35] Shalyt-Margolin. A. The Quantum Field Theory Boundaries Applicability and Black Holes Thermodynamics. Int. J. Theor. Phys. **60**, 1858 (2021).
- [36] Steven Weinberg. *The Quantum Theory of Fields, Vol.1,2* (Cambridge University Press, 1995).
- [37] S.Weinberg. *Cosmology* (Oxford University Press, 2008).
- [38] David Brizuela, Claus Kiefer, Manuel Kramer. Quantum-gravity effects for excited states of inflationary perturbations and Salvador Robles-Perez. Phys.Rev. D.**99**, 104007 (2019).
- [39] Jaroslaw Kopinski and Juan A. Valiente Kroon. Bach equation and the matching of spacetimes in conformal cyclic cosmology models. Phys.Rev. D.**106**, 084039 (2022).